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The Sources of Budget Gaps in the Official Primary Education System

Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh

Abstract

This study seeks to pinpoint the source of the differences between the budgets allocated to primary schools from different sectors and with different supervisory authorities, and to examine whether there is a bias in budgeting, over the years 2014–2023.¹ To do so, the study examines the variables that influence total expenditure per class and per student and examines the differences between schools from different sectors according to these factors. Subsequently, an empirical estimation presents the impact of each variable on the differences in budgeting for each sector (controlling for the influence of the other factors). The research is based on data from schools defined as Official primary regular schools (six-year or eight-year).

The findings reveal that the budgeting process for primary schools is largely based on transparent formulas accessible to the public, and that most of the differences in allocation between the sectors and supervisory authorities do not stem from arbitrary decisions but rather from these budgeting formulas. The research also shows that during the period under review, the budgeting disparities between school from different sectors and with different supervisory authorities have been significantly reduced.

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1 This is the fourth in a series of papers on the subject of budgeting in the education system (Blass & Bleikh, 2018; 2020; 2024).

Introduction

The Ministry of Education's budget is the second largest among government ministries, and, in 2024, it amounted to nearly NIS 83 billion (excluding the development budget). In recent years, there has been an increase in both the overall budget and the expenditure per class and per student. Against this backdrop, it is important to examine how the allocation of the budget among the different parts of the education system is determined. Is it primarily derived from existing, transparent budgeting formulas, or does it implement a deliberate, yet hidden, policy designed to favor certain segments of the student population over others? Naturally, the latter possibility might be based on preferences that are difficult to track, thereby undermining public transparency. The current study examines the disparities in budgeting among the sectors and over the supervisory authorities for the years 2014 through 2023.²

This study focuses on Official regular education (excluding special education) within the education system and the variables affecting the budget allocation. It does not include schools with the status of "Recognized but Unofficial" and "Exempt," due to the different principles of budgeting and operation that apply to them. Furthermore, it does not address Official Haredi primary education, which was established only recently and in which the number of students during the period under consideration is negligible — approximately 12,000 students in the 2023–2024 academic year in primary education, representing about 1.5% of students in these age groups.

School budgeting methods for Official primary regular education

Schools in Israel and around the world are usually budgeted according to rules defined by the authorities responsible for education, whether at the national level or at lower levels, such as regional or municipal (Blass & Bleikh, 2018; Ross & Levačić, 1999). The clearer and well-defined the budgeting formulas, there will be less freedom of action for the heads of the education system to show preference for one sector or to discriminate against another. The budget

2 Sector is differentiated by language of instruction, that is, Hebrew and Arabic-speaking schools while supervisory authority indicates whether the school is a "non-religious" or religious one within the Hebrew or Arab education system.

for primary schools in Israel is determined through three main channels: the basic standard allocation, designated budgetary baskets allocated according to a formula, and other baskets for which there are no clear rules. Below is a breakdown for the first two channels.

The basic standard allocation

The formulas for the standard hours of primary schools reflect two very important policy decisions.³

The first decision stipulates that the majority of the budget allocated to schools is based on the number of classes rather than the number of students. In terms of the per-student budget, this decision gives an advantage to small classes. The justification for this decision is the desire to ensure that small schools can receive the minimum number of teaching hours required to implement the curriculum and other necessary functions. This need arose due to the demographic and political circumstances in which the education system operates. The division into different sectors and supervisory authorities — which was determined even before the establishment of the State and was legally codified in the National Education Law of 1953 — has resulted in the creation of many small schools serving minority groups or located in small communities with few students per class, and therefore, budgeting based on the number of students could result in a school being unable to function as required.

The second decision is that the socioeconomic background of the school will also influence the budgeting, as will be detailed later.

3 Since the vast majority of the budget for primary schools in official education originates from the budgeting of the working hours of teachers employed by the Ministry of Education, this study refers to the standard hours. Other cost components such as cleaning staff and secretaries (employed by the local authorities but primarily funded by the Ministry of Education) are also allocated according to formulas published annually by the Ministry of Education.

Following these two decisions, the basic standard hours per class is determined by three factors.⁴

1. **Minimum instruction hours:** The minimum number of hours a student is taught in their class each week. The exact number of these hours varies, and today it stands at 29 weekly hours (hereinafter weekly hours) for Grades 1–2, 31 weekly hours for Grades 3–4, and 32 weekly hours for Grades 5 and higher.⁵

2. **Class size:** Only a class with at least 20 students is budgeted according to the minimum instruction hours. To address the educational challenges that arise from having many students in a class, each additional student beyond the 20th (up to the maximum number of students for budgeting purposes) entitles the class to an additional budget allocation. If the number of students is less than 20, the class is budgeted at only half of the basic standard's allocation. In 2023, the percentage of teaching hours allocated according to the basic standard allocation with an addition for class size amounted to 63% of all teaching hours (see Appendix Figure 1).⁶

Figure 1 depicts the effects of the number of students in a class on the average budget per class and per student in terms of weekly hours (for Grades 1–2, for illustrative purposes only). As expected, an increase in the number of students raises the class budget. This additional allocation grows at a steady rate up to the 35th student and then increases at a faster pace up to the 40th student.⁷

4 See Ministry of Education, 2022a.

5 The term “weekly hour” has a double meaning. It can refer to hours that students are in a classroom and it is also a budgetary term — not necessarily an hour spent by students in the classroom — but a definition of the cost of a teacher's salary on an hourly basis. In the case of a full-time teacher (36 hour per week), this means 1/36 of the teacher's annual salary.

6 It is worth noting that the relative share of the compensation for class size in the total teaching hours has decreased over the years. This is due to the reduction in class size and changes in the compensation formula, which have resulted in less generous increments for a larger number of students per class.

7 Despite the Ministry of Education's efforts to limit class size in primary education (to 32–34 students, conditioned on the school's nurturing index), there remains a small number of classes with more than 32 students. This is because sometimes the number of students in a grade does not allow the class to be divided (for example, if there are 33 students in a grade when the upper limit is 32, dividing the class would result in two classes with fewer than 20 students). In such cases, the Ministry of Education compensates the school so that every student beyond the 32nd up to the 40th student entitles the school to an additional 3 weekly hours in Grades 1–2 and 2 weekly hours in Grades 3–6 (Ministry of Education, 2022a).

At the same time, the per-student budget decreases as the number of students in the class increases.

An important point to note: in terms of the class budget, the rates of change for the class size compensation are quite moderate, ranging between 0.3% and 5.2% up to the 35th student.⁸ Although the class size compensation becomes more generous starting with the 36th student, it is an exception rather than the rule. In practice, almost no classes have more than 32 students (Figure 5 below). In contrast, in terms of the per-student budget, the model predicts a sharp decline ranging from 4.4% to 39.9%.⁹

Figure 1. Per class and per student budget: Basic standard hours per class and the compensation for class size, Grades 1-2

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education, 2022a

8 For example, the budget for a class with 21 students (basic standard plus class size compensation) would be 0.3% higher compared to a class with 20 students. The budget for a class with 35 students would be 5.2% higher compared to a class with 20 students.

9 For example, the per-student budget in a class with 21 students (basic standard plus class size compensation) would be 4.4% lower compared to the per-student budget in a class with 20 students; the per-student budget in a class with 35 students would be 39.9% lower compared to the per-student budget in a class with 20 students.

3. **The Nurture Index:** The school socioeconomic index: As noted, the second policy decision related to the basic standard is to set a different maximum threshold for calculating class size for budgeting purposes based on the students' socioeconomic background data. In a school whose students come from an advantaged socioeconomic background, the maximum class size was 40 students in 2014, whereas in a school serving students from the weakest socioeconomic background it was 32 students. Over the years, the Ministry of Education has reduced the maximum class size threshold, and in 2024 in Official primary education it stands at 34 students from advantaged socioeconomic background and at 32 for schools that serve students from low socioeconomic background.

There is a substantial difference between the actual class size and the maximum class size for budgeting purposes. An illustration of this is presented in Table 1. For example, in a school with 130 Grade 1 students serving a predominantly advantaged population, the budget will be based on 2 classes of 32 students and 2 classes of 33 students. The basic standard for a Grade 1 class is 29 weekly hours; hence, the 4 classes will receive a total of 116 weekly hours. The maximum additional allocation for class size will amount to 5 weekly hours. Consequently, the budget of the most advantaged school will be 121 weekly hours, with an average class budget of 30.25 weekly hours and a per-student budget of 0.93 weekly hours. In contrast, in a school whose students come from the weakest socioeconomic background, the budget for 130 students will be based on 5 classes of 26 students. Under the basic standard, the school will receive 145 weekly hours, and an additional 3 weekly hours under the maximum class size compensation, so that its budget will amount to 148 weekly hours. The average class budget will be 29.6 weekly hours, and the per-student budget will be 1.14 weekly hours.¹⁰

10 On one hand, this budgeting system prevents reducing the number of classes below the statutory number — due to the upper limit on the number of students per class — and on the other hand, it makes it very difficult to increase the number of classes, as the number of hours allocated by the Ministry will not allow it.

Table 1. An example of the method of per class and per student budget calculations, including basic standard weekly hours and additional compensatory hours for class size, Grade 1

	School from a strong SES	School from a weak SES
Number of students in grade level	130	130
Basic standard allocation of hours	29	29
Maximum number of students per class	40	32
Number of classes in calculation	$130:40 = 3.25$ (4)	$130:32 = 4.06$ (5)
Budgeted classes	2 classes of 32 students 2 classes of 33 students	5 classes of 26 students
Total weekly hours per standard basic (A)	$29*4 = 116$	$29*5 = 145$
Compensatory hours for large classes (B)	$1.2*2 + 1.3*2 = 5$	$0.6*5 = 3$
Total weekly hours (A + B)	121	148
Total weekly hours per class	30.25	29.60
Total weekly hours per student	0.93	1.14

Note: The number in parentheses is the number of classes used in the calculation.

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education, 2022a

Both measures — setting a maximum class size threshold and providing budgetary compensation for size — positively impact the quality of life and learning in schools. The first contributes to reducing class sizes, while the second compensates for the challenges associated with learning in large classes.

Targeted baskets

In this section, budgetary baskets of services that are designated to achieve specific declared objectives of the Ministry of Education are transferred to schools. The size of the budgets is determined by a formula, and the schools are directed regarding their use.

Nurture Basket: The purpose of this basket is to enable schools serving students from weaker socioeconomic backgrounds to provide their students with the necessary assistance to overcome the challenges they encounter during their studies due to their living conditions, in order to narrow

educational gaps between them and students from stronger socioeconomic backgrounds. Weininger (2019) points to an increase in the share of hours from the Nurture Basket out of the total teaching hours in a classroom setting in primary education, from 5.6% in 2014 to 11.5% in 2019. The allocation of the budget from the Nurture Basket is based on a formula that relies heavily on the Nurture Index.¹¹

Inclusion and integration basket: The purpose of this fund is to enable regular schools to mainstream students with special needs into their regular classes. Since it is allocated according to a formula, it can also be considered part of the basic standard. The fundamental assumption behind the inclusion and integration basket is that it is likely that every school has students with special needs and that their proportion is fairly similar across schools. The amount of the inclusion fund provided to schools is 7.7% of the total number of students studying in regular classes multiplied by 1.85 weekly hours.¹²

Students with special needs experiencing severe difficulties resulting in low functioning receive an additional 2.7 teaching hours as an individual basket. This additional allocation is granted only after an individual assessment, and the number of students receiving it varies between schools. The number of these students has grown significantly in recent years following Amendment No. 11 to the Special Education Law, which stipulated that certain types of disabilities automatically qualify students for an individual basket. Thus, if in 2014 approximately 7% of all students with special needs in regular schools (mainstreamed students) were eligible for an individual fund, today their share reaches 24% (Blass, 2023).

11 The school's Nurture Index is determined based on the characteristics of its students. The index is influenced by four components: the education level of the most educated parent (40%); the per capita family income (20%); the peripherality of the school (20%); and a combination of immigration and the share of immigrants from countries characterized by low HDI index as distressed (20%). A high Nurture Index characterizes populations from a low socioeconomic level, whereas a low Nurture Index characterizes students from advantaged populations. For further details, see the Portal for Authorities and Education Costs, [School Nurture Indices](#).

12 See Ministry of Education, 2021. It is evident that this is an overly sweeping assumption — some schools benefit from it while others are adversely affected. In our estimation, there is room to incorporate additional variables, such as socioeconomic background data and others that would influence the amount of the inclusion and integration fund.

Prayer hours: The additional allocation for prayer hours in primary schools within the State-religious education system amounts to one teaching hour per standard class (that is, a class for budgeting purposes, as explained above).

New immigrants and returning residents basket: The allocation formulas for assisting new immigrants and returning residents take into account the country of immigration and the length of the student's stay in that country.

Factors influencing per class and per student budgeting

A comparison between the class and per-student budgets in regular primary education schools indicates several key variables that influence the budget allocated to a school. These variables, as will be explained, account for a significant share of the differences in the class and per-student budgets between schools.

Nurture Index: The school's Nurture Index affects the total weekly hours the school receives from the Nurture basket as well as the class size used for budgeting, which is not uniform across schools, as explained above. In addition, the Nurture Index plays a role in determining the allocation amount within some of the other baskets, including the decision on whether to include the school in the long school day program.

School size: The size of the school is one of the most influential variables on the educational experience of both students and teachers, and it is equally significant from a budgeting perspective, due to its large impact on class size when the primary budgeting unit is the class rather than the student. A school's size is greatly affected by the number of children residing in the enrollment area it serves, and the division into zones is determined by the local authority based on rules set by the Ministry of Education regarding the maximum allowable walking distance from a student's home to the school and the educational considerations regarding school size (maximum, minimum, and desired). The implementation of the system according to the uniform rules set by the Ministry of Education affects the size of the enrollment area (when the population is dense, the enrollment area will shrink, and vice versa). Despite these considerations, the local authority has considerable discretion in this area, provided it does not significantly deviate from the rules.

Special education: In regular schools that have separate special education classes, the basic standard for these classes is higher than that of regular classes.

Long school day: Some primary schools are included in the long school day program. Under this program, standard classes are budgeted based on a minimum of 37 weekly hours. This represents a significant increase of approximately 23% compared to the minimum standard for a class, which is around 30 weekly hours.

The first order for the implementation of the long school day law was published by Minister of Education Zevulun Hammer several months after the law was passed in 1997. This order stipulated that “the long school day in the 1997/1998 academic year will apply in schools located in rehabilitation neighborhoods, educational welfare areas, National Priority A settlements, confrontation line areas, settlements identified as having a high rate of unemployment, and settlements from the first and second clusters of the socioeconomic index Weissblei, 2018).¹³ The wording of the order also reflects the primary objectives of the law: reducing learning and educational gaps and assisting in integration of parents into the workforce.

Sector and supervisory authority: The impact of the supervisory authority is evident in the State-religious education system and in schools in the Arab education sector. State-religious schools are smaller and, on average, have a higher Nurture Index, which explains part of the differences in budgeting. In addition, they receive an extra budget allocation for prayer hours. Schools in the Arab education sector have received various supplements under the Five-Year Development Plans designed to reduce gaps.¹⁴

13 The proportion of institutions participating in the long school day program increases with the rise in the Nurture Index. See Appendix Figure 2.

14 For example, the 5-year development program in the Arabic-speaking sector for the years 2013–2018; [The Five-Year Development Program for the Arab Sector](#) according to Government Decision 292 dated August 1, 2021.

Methodology

Data sources: The study utilizes two Ministry of Education databases for the years 2014–2023: (a) Transparency in Education: This database is reported on the website of the Administration for Economy and Budgets and provides information regarding the budgets allocated at the school level and on teacher characteristics at the school level; (b) A Wide Perspective: A data system that provides information on the characteristics of schools.

Study population: The study encompasses 1,700–2,000 schools in Official regular State primary education over the years. In 2023, 793,000 students studied in Official regular State primary education.¹⁵ The Arab sector includes the Druze and the Bedouins. Budget data reported on the Ministry of Education website for schools does not include the budgets transferred to them by local authorities, parents, and NGOs.

Calculation of the average expenditure per class and per student: The Ministry of Education calculates the budget per class and per student in Official regular State primary education in groups by sector and by supervisory authority by summing all the budgets transferred to schools (numerator) and dividing them by the total number of classes/students in regular primary education (denominator) in each group.

In this study, the average per class and per student is calculated differently: in the first step, the budget per class/per student is calculated separately for each school, and in the second step, these budgets are averaged. This approach is reflected in the multivariate analysis; therefore, to maintain consistency, we will use this method throughout the study.

Characteristics of the Official regular education system

This section describes Official regular State primary education from three central aspects: the composition of the student population; class size according to the characteristics of the school; and budgeting per class and per student.

15 For the numbers of students in each sector and type of supervision, see Appendix Table 1. The data also include a small number of students in Grades 7–9 who are classified as studying in primary education (approximately 3.5% of the students over the years).

Figure 2 shows the changes that occurred between 2014 and 2023 in the composition of Official regular State primary education students in terms of the distribution between supervisory authority and sectors. The figure shows that during this period the proportions of State Hebrew education and State-religious education increased, while that of State Arab education decreased by 4 percentage points. It is important to emphasize that State-religious education grew at a relatively faster pace. The share of integrated special education students in regular State education does not exceed 4%. However, the data presented in Figure 3 indicate a trend of growth in the relative share of special education students in Jewish education, particularly in State Hebrew education.¹⁶

Figure 2. Students in regular classes by sector and supervisory authority, as a percent of all students

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

¹⁶ In the years 2014–2023, the number of students in the system increased by 16%, while the number of students in regular classes grew by 15% and the number in non-regular classes increased by 43%. During the same period, the number of classes in the system grew by 24%, while regular classes increased by 22% and non-regular classes by 55%. Appendix Table 2 shows the percentage of special education classes and special education students studying in separate classes in regular State primary education during 2014–2023.

Figure 3. Students in special education in regular schools by sector and supervisory authority, as a percent of all students

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Table 2 presents the distribution of students across sectors and supervisory authorities according to the characteristics of the schools at two points in time: in 2014 and in 2023.¹⁷ The data reveal significant differences between sectors and supervisory authorities in general, as well as changes in these differences over the examined period. For example, in 2023, the proportion of students in the two Nurture Index quintiles from strong socioeconomic backgrounds (Quintiles 1–2) in State Hebrew education stood at 67% and in State-religious education at 63%, whereas in State Arab education there were almost no students in these quintiles. By contrast, the share of students in the two Nurture Index quintiles from weaker socioeconomic backgrounds (Quintiles 4–5) in State Hebrew education was 17% and in State-religious education only 12%, while in State Arab education their proportion was 88%.

17 For the distribution of schools by their characteristics see Appendix Table 3.

Table 2. Distribution of students by school characteristics, 2014 and 2023

	2014			2023		
	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab
Nurture Index quintile						
1 (Strongest)	49%	22%	0%	48%	22%	
2	23%	36%	1%	19%	41%	1%
3	13%	23%	11%	16%	25%	10%
4	9%	13%	26%	10%	10%	26%
5 (Weakest)	6%	6%	62%	7%	2%	62%
Institution size						
Up to 180 students	3%	9%	1%	2%	6%	1%
181–360	22%	41%	16%	20%	39%	21%
361–540	39%	31%	36%	42%	33%	42%
541–720	30%	13%	27%	28%	15%	23%
Over 720	7%	6%	20%	8%	7%	13%
Participation in long school day program						
No	84%	67%	51%	85%	67%	49%
Yes	16%	33%	49%	15%	33%	51%
Special education						
No special education classes	43%	47%	11%	28%	40%	17%
Up to 10% of classes	21%	18%	60%	25%	18%	46%
Over 10% of classes	35%	34%	29%	47%	42%	37%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Furthermore, more than 75% of the students in State Hebrew education and State Arab education study in schools where the student enrollment exceeds 360. In contrast, in State-religious education, fewer students attend large schools, although there is a noticeable trend of growth in this aspect.

In both periods, there were no significant changes in the distribution of students participating in the long school day program: half of the students in the Arab sector participate in this program, one third of the students in State-religious education, and 15%–16% of the students in State Hebrew education

do so. The high participation rate among Arab sector students is due to their lower socioeconomic background and their residence in the Northern and Southern Districts, where this benefit is more prevalent.¹⁸

Most schools in the Arab education system have special education classes, although there was a decline in this percentage (from 89% to 83%). The proportion of schools with special education classes is lower in the Jewish sector overall, but it increased over the period, particularly in State Hebrew education (from 56% to 72%).

A notable point is the improvement in socio economic status in State-religious education and State Arab education, in contrast to a decline in State Hebrew education. Since the education system reflects the socioeconomic transformations occurring in society, an analysis was conducted examining changes over time in per capita income based on data from the Israeli Central Bureau of Statistics Social Survey (Figure 4). The analysis shows that the percentage of families with high per capita income increased at a faster rate among religious Jewish populations (who typically send their children to Hebrew State-religious education) and Arabs.

18 In 2023, 100% of students in the Druze sector had a long school day, 90% in the Bedouin sector had a long school day, and 26% in the Arab sector had the same.

Figure 4. Distribution of income per capita in coupled households

Note: The Social Survey does not allow an examination by household. Thus, for calculation purposes, married men aged 25-54 were analyzed.

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey (various years)

The budgeting model demonstrated in Figure 1 illustrates the importance of class size when distinguishing between what the class receives versus what the student receives in budgetary terms. Table 3 presents the differences in class size among sectors and supervisory authorities according to the characteristics of the schools. As can be seen, the higher the Nurture Index, the lower the average number of students per class. The average number of students per class increases as the size of the schools increases. Additionally, unsurprisingly, an increase in the number of special education classes in the school reduces average class size. In institutions participating in the long school day program, the average class size is significantly lower than that in institutions without

a long school day in State Hebrew education, slightly lower in State-religious education, and almost shows no difference in State Arab education.

Table 3. Average number of students in a class by school characteristics, 2014 and 2023

	2014			2023		
	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab
Nurture Index quintile						
1 (Strongest)	29.8	28.0		26.6	26.0	
2	27.7	25.8	26.2	25.6	24.9	26.7
3	25.6	24.8	26.6	25.1	24.3	25.4
4	24.6	23.3	25.7	24.0	23.6	24.4
5 (Weakest)	23.8	21.9	25.5	22.7	22.3	23.7
Institution size						
Up to 180 students	24.4	22.8	24.7	24.5	24.3	24.1
181–360	24.5	24.4	24.0	23.3	23.9	22.6
361–540	28.4	27.1	25.3	25.6	25.7	24.1
541–720	31.0	29.4	26.9	27.8	26.4	26.0
Over 720	33.2	30.4	28.8	29.5	27.8	26.5
Participation in long school day program						
No	28.2	25.6	25.8	25.8	25.0	24.1
Yes	24.9	24.2	25.6	23.8	24.2	24.1
Special education						
Has no special education classes	29.8	26.1	26.5	27.6	26.2	25.8
Up to 10% of classes	28.3	27.2	26.2	27.0	25.3	24.7
Over 10% of classes	24.7	22.7	24.3	23.6	22.8	22.8
Total	27.6	25.1	25.7	25.5	24.7	24.1

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

In public discourse, there is sometimes the claim that it is difficult to learn and teach in a class of 40 students. This is a problem that worries both parents and teachers, who attach great importance to class size and view the reduction of class sizes as a long-desired and important goal — one that is expected to lead to improvements in academic achievement, the learning environment, and teachers' working conditions. Figure 5 demonstrates that in recent years, virtually no students study in schools where the average class size exceeds 32. Claims regarding the difficulty of teaching in a class of 40 belong to a bygone era. Today, 62% of students study in classes with up to 28 students, compared to 40% in 2014. While there are differences between sectors and supervisory authorities in the distribution of students by average class size, the overall trend is a reduction in the percentage of students studying in large classes — a reflection of the Ministry of Education's declared policy.

Figure 5. Distribution of students by the number of students per class, regular classes, 2014 and 2023

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Now, let us turn to describe the distribution of the budget per class and per student in primary education.¹⁹

In this study, as in other studies, the terms gap and inequality are often used. Research on inequality — in Israel as in many other parts of the world — tends to almost automatically assume that reducing gaps between different population

19 It should be noted that the calculation of the average expenditure per class and per student in the tables below — and throughout the study — differs from the calculations used by the Ministry of Education, as explained earlier in the methodology section.

groups (primarily in terms of socioeconomic background) is a positive step, and that widening these gaps is a negative phenomenon. However, when it comes to school budgeting, the issue is more complex, because it is commonly assumed — based on countless studies and accumulated educational experience — that in order to create true equal opportunities, students from weaker socioeconomic backgrounds must be given budgetary priority.

In this context, it is important to distinguish between two situations: (1) a situation in which, at baseline, there is a budgetary advantage for the socioeconomically stronger group — where reducing the budget gap between the weaker and stronger groups reflects an increase in affirmative action; and (2) a situation in which, at baseline, there is a budgetary advantage for the socioeconomically weaker group — in which case reducing the gap between the groups reflects a decrease in affirmative action.

Tables 4 and 5 describe the trends in expenditure per class and per student according to school characteristics. What stands out in these tables is the increase in the budget per class and per student between 2021 and 2023. The main reasons for this are the budget increase during the Covid period and the new salary agreement with the Teachers' Union.²⁰ The tables refer separately to the period 2014–2019 and to the entire period 2014–2023. They should be read both by columns (i.e., comparing differences across school characteristics within each year) and by rows (i.e., examining the changes over the entire period for each characteristic).

It can be observed that for the vast majority of years, the average budgeting per class and per student in State-religious education is the highest, while in State Hebrew education it is the lowest.

An examination of changes in budgeting per class (Table 4) by the Nurture Index indicates an increase of 40% over the entire period in Quintiles 3–5, and an increase of 36% in Quintiles 1–2. Within each year, one almost always sees an increase in the budget per class as the Nurture Index rises. This policy is also reflected in the per-student allocation (Table 5). However, a view over the

20 The data presented in our research include the budgetary supplements that were transferred to schools during the Covid period, unlike the Ministry of Education's budget transparency publications for the academic years 2020–2021 and 2021–2022, which intentionally exclude these supplements to allow for an easier comparison with previous years. As a result, the budgeting data per class and per student in those publications are biased downward relative to the actual situation. See Ministry of Education, 2022b; 2023.

entire period reveals that in fact, in the strongest quintile (Quintile 1), the per-student budgeting increased more compared to the other quintiles.

The data further indicate that an increase in the size of the school reduces the average expenditure per class. It appears that over time, the largest increases in the budget per class characterized smaller schools. The negative correlation between the size of the school and the expenditure per student is very pronounced. These results largely stem from the fact that in larger schools the average number of students per class is higher, as shown in Table 3 previously.

The expenditure per class and per student is much higher in institutions participating in the long school day program compared to those that do not participate in it. In terms of the budget per class, this represents an increase of about 15%–20% over the years, and in terms of per-student expenditure, the gap is even larger — 25%–29%. Throughout the entire period, the budget per class increased by the same amount in institutions with or without a long school day, whereas in per-student expenditure, the rate of growth was slightly higher in institutions that do not participate in the long school day program.

Finally, the data indicate that the rate of growth in the budget per class and per student was slightly higher in schools that have special education classes. In schools where more than 10% of the classes are special education classes, the budgeting is higher compared to other institutions.

Table 4. Expenditure per class in Official regular primary education, by school characteristics

NIS thousands, current prices

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Percent change between 2014 and 2019	Percent change between 2014 and 2023
Sector/Supervisory authority												
State Hebrew	397	411	414	422	424	429	434	489	482	556	8%	40%
State-religious	440	457	465	467	466	469	467	526	514	590	6%	34%
State Arab	402	410	423	435	438	451	453	501	501	566	12%	41%
Nurture Index quintile												
1 (Strongest)	380	390	393	397	397	396	399	457	445	519	4%	36%
2	405	421	426	426	427	430	435	496	484	552	6%	36%
3	417	434	439	448	450	458	457	514	509	585	10%	40%
4	421	432	442	454	454	458	467	520	510	589	9%	40%
5 (Weakest)	429	442	452	465	470	479	484	528	531	601	12%	40%
Institution size												
Up to 180 students	476	497	517	520	519	539	542	604	589	679	13%	42%
181–360	412	425	434	445	448	451	453	507	504	576	10%	40%
361–540	397	410	414	422	423	428	433	487	478	549	8%	38%
541–720	390	403	404	411	411	417	416	471	466	536	7%	38%
Over 720	395	408	409	414	414	420	422	471	462	538	6%	36%

Table 4 (continued). Expenditure per class in Official regular primary education, by school characteristics
NIS thousands, current prices

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Percent change between 2014 and 2019	Percent change between 2014 and 2023
Participation in long school day program												
No	388	399	406	411	413	418	421	480	468	538	8%	39%
Yes	454	472	481	492	495	503	507	550	555	633	11%	39%
Special education												
Has no special education classes	413	426	433	436	436	441	443	502	492	566	7%	37%
Up to 10% of classes	399	411	416	425	427	436	436	486	480	548	9%	37%
Over 10% of classes	411	426	434	443	446	452	457	510	504	577	10%	40%
Total	409	422	429	436	438	444	447	501	494	567	9%	39%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Table 5. Expenditure per student in Official regular primary education, by school characteristics
NIS thousands, current prices

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Percent change between 2014 and 2019	Percent change between 2014 and 2023
Sector/Supervisory authority												
State Hebrew	14.8	15.3	15.6	16.1	16.4	16.6	17.0	19.3	19.2	22.3	12%	51%
State-religious	18.0	18.6	18.8	19.0	19.0	19.1	18.9	21.3	21.0	24.3	6%	34%
State Arab	15.8	16.3	17.2	17.9	18.2	18.8	18.9	20.9	20.9	23.7	19%	50%
Nurture Index quintile												
1 (Strongest)	13.1	13.4	13.6	14.1	14.2	14.4	14.7	17.1	16.8	19.9	10%	52%
2	15.4	16.1	16.2	16.3	16.5	16.7	17.0	19.6	19.3	22.1	9%	44%
3	16.7	17.3	17.7	18.1	18.4	18.7	18.5	20.8	20.9	24.1	12%	44%
4	17.3	17.7	18.1	18.8	19.2	19.3	19.7	21.8	21.3	24.8	12%	43%
5 (Weakest)	17.7	18.4	18.9	19.7	19.9	20.3	20.6	22.6	22.9	26.0	15%	47%
Institution size												
Up to 180 students	21.0	21.8	21.9	22.5	22.5	22.7	22.9	25.3	25.3	28.5	8%	36%
181–360	17.2	17.8	18.2	18.7	19.0	19.2	19.3	21.7	21.7	25.1	12%	46%
361–540	14.7	15.2	15.6	16.2	16.4	16.8	17.0	19.3	19.0	22.0	14%	49%
541–720	13.3	13.8	14.1	14.5	14.7	15.0	15.1	17.3	17.2	19.9	12%	49%
Over 720	13.1	13.4	13.7	14.2	14.4	14.7	14.8	16.7	16.5	19.3	12%	48%

Table 5 (continued). Expenditure per student in Official regular primary education, by school characteristics
NIS thousands, current prices

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Percent change between 2014 and 2019	Percent change between 2014 and 2023
Participation in long school day program												
No	14.6	15.0	15.5	15.9	16.1	16.4	16.6	19.0	18.6	21.6	12%	47%
Yes	18.6	19.3	19.7	20.3	20.6	20.9	21.1	23.0	23.5	26.8	13%	44%
Special education												
Has no special education classes	15.0	15.5	15.8	16.1	16.1	16.5	16.6	18.9	18.6	21.4	10%	42%
Up to 10% of classes	14.9	15.4	15.8	16.2	16.5	16.9	16.9	18.9	18.8	21.4	13%	44%
Over 10% of classes	17.5	18.0	18.4	19.0	19.3	19.5	19.8	22.1	22.0	25.3	12%	45%
Total	15.9	16.4	16.8	17.2	17.5	17.8	18.0	20.2	20.1	23.1	12%	46%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

As noted previously, the budgeting in State Arab education — both per class and per student — is the second highest overall. This can also be seen in Tables 6 and 7 (last column). However, within every Nurture Index quintile, the budgeting per class and per student in State Arab education is the lowest, and the degree of differentiation (i.e., the increase in budgeting as the Nurture Index rises) across the quintiles is significantly lower compared to the Jewish sector, especially relative to State-religious education, where the degree of differentiation is the highest.

Over the period, the budgeting gaps between State-religious education and State Hebrew education within the Nurture Index quintiles have narrowed. For example, in 2014 the budgeting per class in the weakest quintile in State-religious education was 19% higher compared to the weakest quintile in State Hebrew education, whereas by 2023 the gap in budgeting per class had decreased to 11%. In terms of per student budgeting, in 2014 the weakest quintile in State-religious education was allocated 33% more than in State Hebrew education, whereas by 2023 this gap had reduced to 17%. A comparison between State Arab education and State-religious education shows that in 2014 the budgeting per class in the weakest quintile in State Arab education was 23% lower, while by 2023 the gap narrowed to 19%. In per student budgeting terms, the differences in the weakest quintile between State Arab education and State-religious education decreased from 36% to 27%.

Table 6. Expenditure per class in Official primary education by sector and supervisory authority and the Nurture Index, 2014 and 2023

NIS thousands, current prices

	1 (Strongest)	2	3	4	5 (Weakest)	Total
2014						
Budget per class						
State Hebrew	377	393	409	425	445	397
State-religious	397	424	439	460	532	440
State Arab		377	393	396	407	402
Differentiation (budget gap relative to Quintile 1)						
State Hebrew		4%	8%	13%	18%	
State-religious		7%	11%	16%	34%	
State Arab			4%	5%	8%	
Budget disparities						
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	5%	8%	7%	8%	19%	11%
State Arab relative to State Hebrew		-4%	-4%	-7%	-8%	1%
State Arab relative to State-religious		-11%	-10%	-14%	-23%	-9%
2023						
Budget per class						
State Hebrew	513	535	588	603	646	556
State-religious	544	572	605	641	715	590
State Arab		496	521	556	579	566
Differentiation (budget gap relative to Quintile 1)						
State Hebrew		4%	15%	17%	26%	
State-religious		5%	11%	18%	31%	
State Arab			5%	12%	17%	
Budget disparities						
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	6%	7%	3%	6%	11%	6%
State Arab relative to State Hebrew		-7%	-11%	-8%	-10%	2%
State Arab relative to State-religious		-13%	-14%	-13%	-19%	-4%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Table 7. Expenditure per student in Official primary education by sector and supervisory authority and the Nurture Index, 2014 and 2023

NIS thousands, current prices

	1 (Strongest)	2	3	4	5 (Weakest)	Total
2014						
Budget per student						
State Hebrew	12.8	14.5	16.3	17.7	18.9	14.8
State-religious	14.3	16.7	18.0	20.0	25.2	18.0
State Arab		14.4	14.9	15.5	16.1	15.8
Differentiation (budget gap relative to Quintile 1)						
State Hebrew		13%	27%	38%	48%	
State-religious		16%	26%	39%	76%	
State Arab			3%	7%	12%	
Budget disparities						
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	12%	15%	11%	13%	33%	22%
State Arab relative to State Hebrew		-1%	-8%	-12%	-15%	7%
State Arab relative to State-religious		-13%	-17%	-22%	-36%	-12%
2023						
Budget per student						
State Hebrew	19.6	21.2	24.1	25.7	29.0	22.3
State-religious	21.3	23.1	25.3	27.4	33.8	24.3
State Arab		19.1	20.6	23.0	24.6	23.7
Differentiation (budget gap relative to Quintile 1)						
State Hebrew		9%	23%	31%	48%	
State-religious		9%	19%	29%	59%	
State Arab			8%	21%	29%	
Budget disparities						
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	9%	9%	5%	7%	17%	9%
State Arab relative to State Hebrew		-10%	-14%	-10%	-15%	6%
State Arab relative to State-religious		-18%	-19%	-16%	-27%	-2%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Naturally, in public discourse there is often a focus on the bottom line, that is, on the data at the average per class and per student level. The budgeting data presented in Table 8 demonstrate a central trend of reducing the gaps in per class and per student budgeting between State-religious education and both State Hebrew and State Arab education. Between 2014 and 2023, the gap in the average per class expenditure between State-religious and State Hebrew education narrowed from 11% to 6%, and the gap in per student expenditure decreased from 22% to 9%. Similarly, the gaps between State Arab and State-religious education in per class expenditure shrank from 9% to 4%, and in per student expenditure from 12% to 2%.

These results can be explained by a combination of a number of central processes. In State-religious education, there was an improvement in socioeconomic conditions accompanied by an increase in the relative weight of students studying in larger schools — processes that worked to reduce the overall budgeting in that sector. In contrast, in State Hebrew education there was a decline in socioeconomic status, along with an increase in the number of classes and special education students — processes that led to an increase in budgeting per class and per student. The rise in budgeting in State Arab education resulted from the state's recognition of the large budgeting gaps between the Jewish and Arab sectors and the imperative to reduce them (indeed, several five-year development programs for the Arab sector were formulated during the period, addressing education among other areas).

Table 8. Disparities in expenditure per class and per student in Official primary education, 2014–2023

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Per class										
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	11%	11%	12%	11%	10%	9%	8%	8%	7%	6%
State Arab relative to State Hebrew	1%	0%	2%	3%	3%	5%	4%	3%	4%	2%
State Arab relative to State-religious	-9%	-10%	-9%	-7%	-6%	-4%	-3%	-5%	-3%	-4%
Per student										
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	22%	21%	21%	18%	16%	15%	11%	10%	9%	9%
State Arab relative to State Hebrew	7%	7%	10%	11%	11%	13%	11%	8%	9%	6%
State Arab relative to State-religious	-12%	-12%	-9%	-6%	-4%	-1%	0%	-2%	0%	-2%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Multivariate analysis

To examine in depth the correlation between the expenditure per class/per student and the factors influencing budgeting, a multivariate analysis using linear regression was conducted. The analysis focused on two central aspects:

1. The effect of each factor (sector and supervisory authority, the Nurture Index, institution size, etc.) on budgeting, holding all other characteristics constant.
2. The relative contribution of each factor to the model's explanatory power.²¹

The results of the analysis for the factors affecting budgeting per class and per student are reported in Appendix Tables 4 and 5. The dependent variable is the natural logarithm of budgeting per class and per student, and the main explanatory variables are sector and supervisory authority, the Nurture Index, institution size, participation in the long school day program, and the presence or absence of special education classes in the school.²²

21 This calculation was carried out using Shapley decomposition. See the use of this procedure by Heuettner & Sunder, 2012.

22 Additional variables included in the multivariate model are: whether the school includes only Grades 1–6; whether there are new immigrants at the school; and in which socioeconomic cluster the school locality is located.

The following is a summary of the results by central variables:

Nurture Index: Analysis of budgeting per class shows that the higher the Nurture Index — meaning the weaker the socioeconomic status of the population is — the higher the allocation per class across the system, and this relationship holds consistently over the years. A similar conclusion resulted from the models for budgeting per student. However, the degree of differentiation (i.e., the increase in budgeting as the Nurture Index rises) in per student budgeting is higher compared to that for per class budgeting. This is due to the fact that schools in higher Nurture Index quintiles are characterized, on average, by classes with fewer students (see Table 3 above).

Institution size: The analysis of budgeting per class indicates that in the smallest schools, serving up to 180 students, the expenditure per class is the highest — and significantly so — compared to larger schools. Moreover, the differences among the other schools (apart from the smallest ones) are not pronounced. However, when looking at budgeting per student, it is evident that the budgeting consistently decreases as the school size increases. As presented in Table 3 above, larger schools tend to have classes with a higher number of students, and therefore, according to the budgeting mechanism, the expenditure per student in these institutions tends to be lower.

Special education: In general, the presence of separate special education classes does not significantly increase the average expenditure per class compared to schools without such classes.²³ However, special education classes in a school serve to significantly increase the per student allocation. This outcome results from the fact that the average number of students per class in schools with special education students is lower than in schools that do not include these students (see Table 3 above).

Long school day: Participation in the long school day program provides an institution with a significant addition to teacher working hours, which is reflected in higher budgeting both per class and per student. The budgeting per class in institutions with a long school day is higher by approximately 11%–15% over the years compared to institutions without a long school day. In terms of budgeting per student, the expenditure is higher by about 12%–16%

23 The data does not allow an analysis of the direct expenditure for special education classes. The percentage of special education classes and special education students in regular schools in Official education is shown in Appendix Table 2.

in institutions that implement the long school day program compared to those that do not.

Sector and supervisory authority: This variable, which lies at the core of the study, was examined both before and after controlling for the other explanatory variables (see Table 9).²⁴ The following results describe the budgeting gaps between the different parts of the system after controlling for institutional characteristics.

- It is evident that the gap between State Hebrew education and State-religious education has narrowed. In terms of budgeting per class, the gap shrank from approximately 5% at the beginning of the period to less than 2% in recent years, and in terms of budgeting per student, it decreased from 9% to a gap of less than 3% in recent years.
- State Arab education is allocated less funding than State Hebrew education both per class and per student. This result is consistent with the findings in Tables 6 and 7, which show that the allocation in each Nurture Index quintile in the Arab sector is lower than in the Jewish sector.
- In terms of budgeting per class, until 2021, the gaps between State Arab education and State-religious education narrowed, but then returned to their level at the beginning of the period. In terms of budgeting per student, the gaps narrowed throughout the entire period (from 14.6% in 2014 to 11.8% in 2023), although in recent years there has once again been an expansion.

24 The results describing the budgeting gaps before controlling for explanatory variables in Table 9 differ slightly from those in Table 8 because Table 8 considered all schools in regular State primary education, whereas Table 9 excluded schools for which complete data were not available for all explanatory variables. In addition, Table 8 is based on average data, while the percentages presented in Table 9 are expressed in log points.

Table 9. Multivariate analysis: Gaps in expenditure per class and per student by sector and supervisory authority, 2014-2023

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Without controlling for explanatory variables										
Gaps in per class budget										
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	9.8%***	10.1%***	10.3%***	9.9%***	9.1%***	8.2%***	7.4%***	6.7%***	5.8%***	5.9%***
State Arab relative to State Hebrew	1.6%***	0.2%	2.6%***	3.6%***	3.9%***	5.7%***	5.3%***	3.1%***	4.9%***	3.1%***
State Arab relative to State-religious	-8.2%***	-9.9%***	-7.7%***	-6.3%***	-5.2%***	-2.4%***	-2.1%**	-3.7%***	-0.9%	-2.8%***
Gaps in per student budget										
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	19.0%***	19.1%***	18.1%***	16.7%***	14.6%***	13.3%***	11.6%***	9.8%***	8.2%***	8.8%***
State Arab relative to State Hebrew	8.2%***	8.3%***	11.7%***	12.7%***	13.0%***	14.1%***	13.2%***	9.7%***	10.6%***	8.5%***
State Arab relative to State-religious	-10.8%***	-10.9%***	-6.4%***	-4.0%***	-1.6%	0.8%	1.5%	-0.1%	2.4%**	-0.4%
After controlling for explanatory variables										
Gaps in per class budget										
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	5.4%***	5.3%***	4.5%***	4.5%***	3.6%***	2.2%***	1.2%*	1.4%**	0.5%	1.6%**
State Arab relative to State Hebrew	-6.7%***	-10.2%***	-9.1%***	-9.5%***	-10.7%***	-8.7%***	-7.9%***	-6.4%***	-8.3%***	-10.4%***
State Arab relative to State-religious	-12.1%***	-15.5%***	-13.6%***	-14.0%***	-14.2%***	-10.9%***	-9.1%***	-7.8%***	-8.8%***	-12.0%***
Gaps in per student budget										
State-religious relative to State Hebrew	8.5%***	7.5%***	6.7%***	6.6%***	4.8%***	3.9%***	2.7%***	2.4%***	1.4%*	2.9%***
State Arab relative to State Hebrew	-6.2%***	-8.2%***	-6.7%***	-6.7%***	-7.2%***	-6.0%***	-6.1%***	-6.3%***	-7.9%***	-8.9%***
State Arab relative to State-religious	-14.6%***	-15.6%***	-13.4%***	-12.9%***	-12.0%***	-10.0%***	-8.8%***	-8.7%***	-9.3%***	-11.8%***

Note: The percent in this table are presented in log points, as is common practice. Significance levels: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Contribution of explanatory variables in budgetary differences among schools

Table 10 presents the results of a statistical analysis that quantifies the relative contribution of the variables in explaining the variance in budgeting per class and per student. The table ranks the groups of explanatory variables, from highest to lowest, according to their contribution to explaining the variance in 2023. The results indicate that the percentage of variance explained in the models for budgeting per class (57%–65% over the years) is lower compared to the models examining budgeting per student (71%–79%). This finding is consistent with the characteristics of the budgeting model presented above (Figure 1), according to which the changes in budgeting per class due to an increase in the number of students per class are much less significant than the changes in budgeting per student. Furthermore, a significant portion of the variance in budgeting per class and per student is related to factors embedded in the budgeting formulas (school size, the Nurture Index, participation in the long school day program, and the presence of special education classes).

The estimation for budgeting per class illustrates the combined importance of the factors that align with the idea of differential budgeting which aims to compensate schools serving socioeconomically disadvantaged populations. For example, the Nurture Index, the long school day, and the socioeconomic cluster of the locality together explain 37%–48% of the variance in budgeting per class over the years.²⁵ In contrast, the estimation for budgeting per student emphasizes the impact of school size and the presence of special education classes. As noted, these variables are correlated with class size, and according to the budgeting model (Figure 1 above), this translates into a larger impact on budgeting per student.

The contribution of the variable sector and supervisory authority, which is at the heart of this research, is relatively limited in both the models for budgeting per class and for budgeting per student. In particular, over time, the contribution of this variable to explaining the variance gradually decreases.

25 Alternatively, this is 63%–73% of the explained variance.

Table 10. Contribution of explanatory variables in explaining the budget variance among schools

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Per class										
Long school day	25.8%	29.3%	26.2%	27.0%	26.7%	27.1%	26.0%	18.9%	21.5%	21.6%
Nurture Index quintile	6.6%	6.7%	6.8%	9.3%	9.4%	11.7%	11.5%	9.8%	11.1%	9.8%
School size	12.1%	11.4%	12.6%	12.1%	11.8%	10.7%	12.9%	15.9%	10.2%	9.2%
Locality SES cluster	4.3%	4.5%	5.7%	6.4%	8.1%	9.2%	8.0%	7.6%	9.2%	9.0%
Sector and supervisory authority	7.9%	9.5%	7.6%	7.1%	6.4%	4.5%	3.6%	3.9%	3.0%	4.3%
Special education	0.7%	0.7%	0.8%	0.9%	1.0%	1.6%	1.6%	1.3%	1.5%	1.8%
Other variables	1.0%	1.2%	1.0%	0.6%	0.7%	0.5%	0.5%	1.0%	0.6%	0.8%
Unexplained variance	41.5%	36.8%	39.2%	36.6%	35.9%	34.8%	35.9%	41.6%	42.8%	43.5%
Per student										
School size	26.7%	26.7%	24.8%	22.8%	21.8%	20.0%	20.1%	22.9%	19.7%	18.8%
Special education	8.7%	8.3%	9.7%	10.8%	11.8%	12.0%	12.3%	13.5%	13.5%	15.6%
Long school day	14.7%	16.5%	15.2%	16.0%	16.6%	16.4%	16.2%	12.3%	13.7%	13.6%
Nurture quintile	13.8%	13.4%	13.9%	14.9%	14.6%	15.5%	15.1%	12.9%	13.2%	11.3%
Locality SES cluster	5.9%	5.8%	7.1%	7.1%	8.4%	8.8%	8.4%	7.6%	8.5%	8.0%
Sector and supervisory authority	7.8%	7.6%	6.6%	5.9%	4.9%	4.3%	3.6%	3.2%	2.7%	3.2%
Other variables	0.9%	1.0%	0.9%	0.7%	0.7%	0.6%	0.6%	0.5%	0.6%	0.6%
Unexplained variance	21.4%	20.7%	21.8%	21.9%	21.2%	22.3%	23.7%	27.2%	28.2%	29.0%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Conclusion

In light of the differences in budgeting per class and per student among schools from different sectors and supervisory authorities, we sought to determine their source and examine whether these gaps have changed over time.

Our research shows that most of the differences in funding per class and per student across parts of the system stem from the funding formulas used by the Ministry of Education. These formulas naturally reflect the positions and values of those who established them, and it is possible that decision makers with different worldviews and values would have set different funding rules and assigned different weights to the factors composing them — something that would have led to different outcomes. For example, it is likely that increasing the Nurture basket would have reduced the budgetary gap between Jewish and Arab education, and that expanding participation in the long school day program in State Hebrew education would have narrowed the gaps between it and State-religious education. However, given that the funding rules have hardly changed despite government turnovers over the years, it must be assumed that most of the differences in allocation between sectors and supervisory authorities stem from the funding formulas rather than from arbitrary decisions — decisions that lack legislative anchoring and are made by one minister or another or by other senior officials in the system, influenced by extraneous considerations.

Contrary to the public perception, as early as 2014 the variable sector and supervisory authority had a relatively small contribution to the variance in budgeting (8% per class and per student), and by 2023 it had further shrunk to only 4% per class and 3% per student. As found in our study, the variables with the highest contribution to the variance in *budgeting per class* are the presence or absence of a long school day (22%) and the Nurture Index quintile (10%), with the former decreasing in importance over the period and the latter increasing. In contrast, for *budgeting per student* in 2023, the two variables with the highest contribution are institution size (19%) and the presence of special education classes (16%). The differences in the impact of the various variables between budgeting per student and budgeting per class largely stem from the budgeting method, which is based more on the class than on the individual student, as described above.

In this context, it is important to note — as also emerged in our study on budgeting for upper-secondary education (Blass & Bleikh, 2024) — that the narrowing of the gaps in budgeting per class and per student reflects, among other things, a broader trend of improvement in the socioeconomic status of religious parents, who typically send their children to State-religious education. This was manifested by an increase in the percentage of students studying in schools from stronger socioeconomic backgrounds, and as a consequence, the budgeting per class and per student in State-religious education decreased. This aligns with the principle of differential budgeting, according to which schools serving students from stronger socioeconomic backgrounds receive lower funding than schools serving students from weaker socioeconomic backgrounds.

With regard to the issue of narrowing the gaps in budgeting per class and per student among sectors and supervisory authorities, the data show that after controlling for a range of explanatory variables, the gaps between State Hebrew education and State-religious education have narrowed significantly over the past decade. In contrast, between State Hebrew education and State Arab education the gaps have widened, especially in recent years. Between State Arab education and State-religious education, there was a narrowing of the gaps in budgeting per class until 2021, after which the gaps increased and returned to their initial levels. Gaps in per student budgeting have narrowed.

The budgeting method in the Israeli education system varies according to the educational stage. Budgeting for preschools differs from that in primary education and middle-school grades, which in turn is completely different from that in high-school education. A critical analysis of the different budgeting methods, the underlying formulas, and their educational, organizational, and social implications is an important task for future research.

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Appendix

Appendix Figure 1. Standard basic hours per class and compensation for class size as a percent of teaching hours in Official regular primary education

Note: The calculation is based on data for regular classes only. The additional compensation for large class size is based on the basic hours in Official primary education schools (Ministry of Education, 2022a).

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Appendix Figure 2. Share of schools participating in the long school day program, by sector and supervisory authority and by Nurture Index, 2023

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Appendix Table 1. Number of students in regular Official primary education, 2014-2023

	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab	Total
2014	350.6	125.5	206.7	682.9
2015	362.9	130.0	205.2	698.2
2016	371.4	134.3	201.4	707.0
2017	381.9	139.0	201.0	721.9
2018	390.3	142.4	200.2	732.9
2019	399.5	146.7	201.0	747.2
2020	408.4	150.6	201.0	760.1
2021	414.6	155.2	201.8	771.5
2022	418.8	159.6	203.6	781.9
2023	423.8	164.0	205.3	793.1

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Appendix Table 2. Percent of special education classes and special education students in separate classes in Official regular primary education, 2014-2023

	Students	Classes
2014	3.1%	8.2%
2015	3.2%	8.3%
2016	3.2%	8.5%
2017	3.4%	8.7%
2018	3.4%	8.9%
2019	3.4%	8.8%
2020	3.4%	8.9%
2021	3.4%	9.0%
2022	3.6%	9.5%
2023	3.9%	10.2%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Appendix Table 3. Distribution of schools by school characteristics, 2014 and 2023

	2014			2023		
	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab	State Hebrew	State-religious	State Arab
Nurture quintile						
1 (strongest)	42%	18%	0%	43%	20%	
2	23%	32%	1%	19%	39%	1%
3	15%	24%	11%	17%	27%	10%
4	12%	16%	27%	11%	11%	27%
5 (weakest)	9%	10%	60%	10%	3%	61%
Institution size						
Up to 180	8%	22%	3%	7%	15%	4%
181–360	32%	47%	26%	29%	48%	31%
361–540	36%	22%	38%	40%	26%	42%
541–720	21%	6%	22%	20%	8%	16%
Over 720	4%	2%	11%	4%	3%	7%
Participation in long school day						
No	80%	64%	50%	81%	66%	49%
Yes	20%	36%	50%	19%	34%	51%
Special education						
No special education classes	43%	54%	15%	30%	46%	19%
Up to 10% of classes	18%	13%	54%	20%	15%	42%
Over 10% of classes	39%	33%	31%	50%	40%	40%

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Appendix Table 4. Multivariate analysis: Variables influencing per class budget

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
<i>Sector and supervisory authority, Reference group: State Hebrew education</i>										
State-religious	0.0538***	0.0527***	0.0446***	0.0454***	0.0356***	0.0215***	0.0116*	0.0141**	0.00502	0.0156**
State Arab	-0.0668***	-0.102***	-0.0915***	-0.0949***	-0.107***	-0.0872***	-0.0793***	-0.0637***	-0.0831***	-0.104***
<i>Nurture Index, Reference group: Quintile 1, strongest</i>										
2	0.0104	0.0205***	0.0116	0.00803	0.00782	0.0186***	0.0246***	0.0236***	0.0222***	0.00918
3	0.0408***	0.0505***	0.0283***	0.0433***	0.0419***	0.0557***	0.0544***	0.0449***	0.0530***	0.0452***
4	0.0526***	0.0655***	0.0514***	0.0622***	0.0518***	0.0596***	0.0693***	0.0625***	0.0711***	0.0746***
5 (weakest)	0.0769***	0.0871***	0.0679***	0.0952***	0.0930***	0.102***	0.102***	0.0745***	0.0956***	0.0912***
<i>Institution size, Reference group: Up to 180 students</i>										
181–360	-0.120***	-0.127***	-0.134***	-0.126***	-0.124***	-0.118***	-0.132***	-0.134***	-0.106***	-0.107***
361–540	-0.117***	-0.120***	-0.142***	-0.142***	-0.149***	-0.145***	-0.157***	-0.156***	-0.137***	-0.131***
541–720	-0.114***	-0.114***	-0.146***	-0.141***	-0.149***	-0.143***	-0.162***	-0.166***	-0.141***	-0.136***
Over 720	-0.110***	-0.109***	-0.137***	-0.142***	-0.149***	-0.141***	-0.159***	-0.158***	-0.142***	-0.123***
<i>Special education students, Reference group: No special education classes</i>										
Up to 10% of classes	-0.0115***	-0.00690*	-0.00401	-0.00155	0.00822*	0.0104**	0.00547	-0.00263	0.00236	0.00205
Over 10% of classes	-0.00781	-0.00219	0.0128**	0.0152***	0.0236***	0.0307***	0.0292***	0.0151***	0.0252***	0.0283***
Has long school day	0.136***	0.150***	0.145***	0.146***	0.145***	0.148***	0.147***	0.108***	0.125***	0.122***

Appendix Table 4 (continued). Multivariate analysis: Variables influencing per class budget

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Has new immigrants	0.000272	-0.00404	0.00515	-0.00328	0.00286	0.00507	0.00691	0.0135**	0.00887	0.00466
Six-year institutions	-0.0259***	-0.0254***	-0.0272***	-0.0172**	-0.0163**	-0.00335	-0.00146	-0.0190***	-0.00107	-0.0138**
Locality SES	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Constant	12.98***	13.02***	13.08***	13.08***	13.10***	13.09***	13.09***	13.21***	13.19***	13.34***
Number of observations	1,659	1,683	1,708	1,741	1,765	1,804	1,834	1,864	1,894	1,915
R ²	0.585	0.632	0.608	0.634	0.641	0.652	0.641	0.584	0.572	0.565

Note: Robust standard errors were used. Significance levels: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Appendix Table 5. Multivariate analysis: Variables influencing per student budget

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
<i>Sector and supervisory authority, Reference group: State Hebrew education</i>										
State-religious	0.0845***	0.0741***	0.0668***	0.0652***	0.0482***	0.0393***	0.0270***	0.0236***	0.0136*	0.0293***
State Arab	-0.0616***	-0.0819***	-0.0669***	-0.0636***	-0.0721***	-0.0603***	-0.0605***	-0.0630***	-0.0793***	-0.0889***
<i>Nurture Index, Reference group: Quintile 1, strongest</i>										
2	0.0421***	0.0501***	0.0456***	0.0275***	0.0304***	0.0320***	0.0269***	0.0316***	0.0278***	0.0173**
3	0.0986***	0.0973***	0.0856***	0.0926***	0.0890***	0.0923***	0.0738***	0.0622***	0.0718***	0.0562***
4	0.135***	0.132***	0.127***	0.122***	0.108***	0.115***	0.114***	0.102***	0.102***	0.0979***
5 (weakest)	0.167***	0.167***	0.165***	0.169***	0.157***	0.164***	0.155***	0.128***	0.146***	0.137***
<i>School size, Reference group: Up to 180 students</i>										
181–360	-0.179***	-0.195***	-0.185***	-0.176***	-0.161***	-0.139***	-0.138***	-0.136***	-0.126***	-0.112***
361–540	-0.278***	-0.301***	-0.290***	-0.279***	-0.265***	-0.243***	-0.235***	-0.230***	-0.229***	-0.212***
541–720	-0.336***	-0.357***	-0.352***	-0.336***	-0.322***	-0.303***	-0.298***	-0.295***	-0.292***	-0.282***
Over 720	-0.384***	-0.404***	-0.398***	-0.385***	-0.371***	-0.342***	-0.343***	-0.334***	-0.333***	-0.301***
<i>Special education students, Reference group: No special education classes</i>										
Up to 10% of classes	0.0600***	0.0624***	0.0654***	0.0636***	0.0708***	0.0660***	0.0648***	0.0556***	0.0640***	0.0619***
Over 10% of classes	0.135***	0.139***	0.152***	0.156***	0.162***	0.160***	0.161***	0.148***	0.164***	0.173***
Has long school day	0.144***	0.157***	0.147***	0.157***	0.159***	0.162***	0.162***	0.125***	0.143***	0.140***

Appendix Table 5 (continued). Multivariate analysis: Variables influencing per student budget

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Has new immigrants	0.00254	0.00647	0.0107	0.00313	0.0123*	0.0129*	0.0121*	0.00943	0.0128*	0.0111
Six-year institutions	0.0242***	0.0315***	0.0323***	0.0338***	0.0282***	0.0248***	0.0228***	0.00337	0.0111	0.00832
Locality SES	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Constant	9.709***	9.781***	9.809***	9.818***	9.838***	9.832***	9.822***	9.950***	9.956***	10.10***
Number of observations	1,659	1,683	1,708	1,741	1,765	1,804	1,834	1,864	1,894	1,915
R ²	0.786	0.793	0.782	0.781	0.788	0.777	0.763	0.728	0.718	0.711

Note: Robust standard errors were used. Significance levels: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education